

Supplementary Materials for SAGE

I. GENERIC HYPOTHESES

In Table I, we provide the generic hypotheses from Harkous et al. [1]. Below, we have provided the heuristics used in [1] to sample potential privacy reviews.

- A review i is labeled as *maybe-privacy* (potential privacy reviews) if $N_E(i, 0.8) \geq 1$ or $N_E(i, 0.7) \geq 3$ or $N_E(i, 0.6) \geq 5$ or $N_E(i, 0.5) \geq 7$.
- A review i is labeled as *maybe-not-privacy* if $N_E(i, 0.4) = 0$.
- Rest of the reviews are labeled as *undetermined*.

II. EXPERIMENTS WITH HEURISTICS

In Table II, we report the detailed analysis of heuristics experiments in SAGE in terms of TP (1-labeled reviews annotated as *maybe-privacy*), TN (0-labeled reviews annotated as *maybe-not-privacy*), FP (0-labeled reviews annotated as *maybe-privacy*), and FN (1-labeled reviews annotated as *maybe-not-privacy*). It can be observed that as we lower the threshold values, the number of FP increases with Set 4, giving the highest FP, i.e., 801 not-privacy reviews (0-labeled) annotated as ‘maybe-privacy’. Set 1 extracts the lowest FP however the number of TP also decreases. therefore, we use 926 ‘maybe-privacy’ reviews extracted using the best-performing Set 2 heuristics for further analysis in SAGE.

III. EXAMPLES OF FALSE POSITIVES

Below we show some examples of reviews that were identified as FP in NLI with their corresponding hypotheses that satisfy set 2 heuristics thresholds.

Example 1:

Emailed to cancel after finding out through forums that this was the only way. got a reply saying they couldn't find my account and asked for another email address. gave them another email address even though i signed in to headspace through the original one i gave them. still no luck. now fobbed off to apple to see if they can find my account and cancel even though i have an android phone and haven't had an iphone for years! please sort it out headspace! being charged 7.95 a month is no fun

Corresponding hypotheses: "Online user activities from various platforms can be connected." and "User is concerned about the permanent storage of their digital transactions."

We can notice that even though the user mentioned different devices, the review is not related to privacy issues and just mentions some technical issues with the subscription system.

TABLE I

GENERIC PRIVACY CONCEPTS AND ASSOCIATED HYPOTHESES FROM [1]

Privacy Concept	Hypotheses
Concepts from Solove's Taxonomy [2]	
Surveillance	1. The user is facing a data surveillance issue.
Interrogation	2. The user is forced to provide information.
Aggregation	3. Personal user information is collected from other sources.
Insecurity	4. The user is concerned about protecting their personal data.
Identification	5. A data anonymity topic is discussed.
Secondary Use	6. The user is concerned about the purposes of personal data access.
Exclusion	7. The user wants to correct their personal information.
Breach of Confidentiality	8. A breach of data confidentiality is discussed.
Disclosure	9. Personal data disclosure is discussed.
Exposure	10. The app exposes a private aspect of the user life.
Increased Accessibility	11. User's data has been made accessible to public.
Blackmail	12. A data blackmailing issue is discussed.
Appropriation	13. User data is being exploited for other purposes.
Distortion	14. False data is presented about the user.
Intrusion	15. Unwanted intrusion to personal info is discussed.
Decisional Interference	16. Intrusion by the government to the user's life is discussed.
Concepts from Wang and Kobsa's Taxonomy [3]	
Notice/Awareness	17. Opting out from personal data collection is discussed.
	18. More access than needed is required.
Data Minimization	
Purpose Specification	19. The reason for data access is not provided.
Collection Limitation	20. Too much personal data is collected.
Use Limitation	21. The data is being used for unexpected purposes.
Onward Transfer	22. Data sharing with third parties is discussed.
Choice/Consent	23. User choice for personal data collection is discussed.
	24. User did not allow access to their personal data.
Generic Privacy Concepts	
Generic Privacy Issues	25. A data privacy topic is discussed.
	26. Protecting user's personal data is discussed.
	27. This is about a privacy feature.
	28. The user is facing a privacy issue.
Positive Privacy Issues	29. The user likes that data privacy is provided.
	30. The user wants privacy.
	31. The app has privacy features.

Example 2:

Was a good app until it logged me out of my account, wouldnt accept my details and when i requested a password reset the email never came. tried multiple times. i paid for a year subscription, it's all gone to waste. dont reccomend.

Corresponding hypotheses: "Unauthorized access to user's private information." and "The user is concerned about protecting their personal data."

TABLE II

NLI EXPERIMENT RESULTS WITH FOUR DIFFERENT SETS OF HEURISTICS IN TERMS OF TP, TN, FP, AND FN. WE USE 926 ‘MAYBE-PRIVACY’ REVIEWS EXTRACTED USING SET 2 (BEST-PERFORMING) FOR FURTHER ANALYSIS IN SAGE.

Heuristics	0-labeled		1-labeled	
	‘maybe-privacy’	‘maybe-not-privacy’	‘maybe-privacy’	‘maybe-not-privacy’
Set 1: $N_E(i, 0.9) \geq 1$ or $N_E(i, 0.8) \geq 3$ or $N_E(i, 0.75) \geq 5$	532	430	297	117
Set 2: $N_E(i, 0.85) \geq 1$ or $N_E(i, 0.75) \geq 3$ or $N_E(i, 0.7) \geq 5$	568	394	358	56
Set 3: $N_E(i, 0.8) \geq 1$ or $N_E(i, 0.7) \geq 3$ or $N_E(i, 0.65) \geq 5$	711	251	367	47
Set 4: $N_E(i, 0.75) \geq 1$ or $N_E(i, 0.65) \geq 3$ or $N_E(i, 0.6) \geq 5$	801	161	379	35

We can notice that the user is discussing a password reset, but that is not due to password compromise or any other privacy concern.

IV. COMPARISON DOMAIN-SPECIFIC AND GENERIC HYPOTHESES (RQ2)

In Table III, we report the detailed analysis of SAGE with domain-specific hypotheses compared to generic hypotheses in terms of TP, TN, FP, and FN at the NLI step.

TABLE III

NLI RESULTS OF SAGE WITH DOMAIN-SPECIFIC HYPOTHESES COMPARED TO GENERIC HYPOTHESES IN TERMS OF TP, TN, FP, AND FN

Hypotheses	0-labeled		1-labeled	
	‘maybe-privacy’	‘maybe-not-privacy’	‘maybe-privacy’	‘maybe-not-privacy’
SAGE with domain-specific hypotheses	568	394	358	56
SAGE with generic hypotheses	761	201	389	25

V. PRIVACY CONCERNS ANALYSIS

Figure 1 and 2 represent the wordcloud and top 50 bigrams, respectively, from privacy reviews extracted using SAGE. The wordcloud represents the top 300 unigrams from all the reviews, where the larger the size of a unigram in a wordcloud, the more frequently it appears in the reviews. The bigram graph represents the top 50 pairs of words that have occurred most frequently among all reviews.

It can be seen that privacy concerns arise due to prevalent issues related to credit card or bank details as highlighted by top bigrams “credit card”, “bank account”, “card info”, “card details”, “card information”, “personal data”, and “card number”. This confidential information is directly related to the subscription model of the apps, as highlighted by the most frequent words “subscription” and “account” in the wordcloud. This analysis also revealed concerns related to unauthorized payments where users are requesting refunds as highlighted by the bigrams “charged year”, “took money”, “charged card”, “app charged”, “want money”, “want refund”, and “refund money”, in addition to the “money” and “charged” words in the wordcloud. Furthermore, wordcloud reveals another concerning issue related to therapists, suggesting that users’

Fig. 1. Wordcloud of privacy reviews that are extracted using SAGE. The most frequent issues are related to therapists, which are specific to the mental health domain. Additionally, we observed significant concerns related to the subscription model and unauthorized payment charges.

highly confidential medical data shared with therapists might not be secured. These concerns highlight the urgent need for privacy-aware solutions in MH applications that can protect users’ confidential personal data.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Harkous, S. T. Peddinti, R. Khandelwal, A. Srivastava, and N. Taft, “Hark: A deep learning system for navigating privacy feedback at scale,” in *2022 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 2469–2486.
- [2] D. J. Solove, “A taxonomy of privacy,” *U. Pa. l. Rev.*, vol. 154, p. 477, 2005.
- [3] Y. Wang, “Privacy-enhancing technologies,” in *Handbook of research on social and organizational liabilities in information security*. IGI Global, 2009, pp. 203–227.

Fig. 2. Top 50 bigrams from privacy reviews that are extracted using SAGE. The most frequent privacy issues are related to credit card or bank account details and unauthorized payment charges.